

Effect of time of artificial lodging and genotype on the yield and yield components of hybrid rice

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The process by which shoots of small-grained cereals are displaced from their vertical position is known as lodging. This usually occurs only after the panicle has emerged and results in the shoots permanently leaning or lying horizontally on the ground. This can reduce grain yield by up to 80% and can cause severe knock-on effects, including reduced grain quality, greater drying costs, and slower harvest (Berry et al 2004). Lodging continues to reduce the yield of modern semidwarf irrigated rice; yet, there are now no good estimates of world yield losses of rice caused by lodging in modern cultivars. In one study in which plants of modern semidwarf rice cultivars were held erect or allowed to lodge naturally, the lodged plants had a 35% reduced yield (reduced by about 2 t ha⁻¹) relative to the plants held erect (IRRI 1986). Lodging reduced canopy photosynthesis by 60–80% relative to erect canopies of deepwater and irrigated rice (Setter et al 1997). Jennings and Sornchai (1964) reported that up to 50% yield loss occurring in the dry season (DS) and 80% in the wet season (WS) resulted from lodging at high nitrogen in varieties with weak culms. The amount of grain loss was directly proportional to the time and severity of lodging. The loss in grain yield was largely attributed to spikelet sterility in the lodged plants.

The objective of this study was to estimate the yield loss of hybrid rice caused by lodging at different grain-filling stages. Micro-plot experiments were conducted in the 2005 DS and 2005 WS at the research field of the International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Philippines. The experiments were conducted in a two-factor randomized complete block design with four replications. The factors were time of artificial lodging (supported, lodged at 10 d after flowering [DAF], lodged at 20 DAF, and lodged at 30 DAF) and genotypes (PSBRc 28, IR75217H, and IR79172H in 2005 DS; IR75217H, IR79118H, and SL-11H in 2005 WS). The genotypes used in this experiment had different levels of lodging resistance, from highly susceptible to resistant.

Fourteen-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 20 Jan 2005 for the DS and on 23 June 2005 for the WS, at a hill spacing of 0.2 × 0.2 m with four seedlings hill⁻¹. Thirty kg P ha⁻¹ as single superphosphate, 40 kg K ha⁻¹ as KCl,

and 5 kg Zn ha⁻¹ as zinc sulfate heptahydrate were applied as basal fertilizers in the 2005 DS, whereas 15 kg P ha⁻¹, 20 kg K ha⁻¹, and 5 kg Zn ha⁻¹ were used in 2005 WS. Nitrogen in the form of urea was applied in a split of 60 kg ha⁻¹ as basal, 40 kg ha⁻¹ at mid-tillering, 60 kg ha⁻¹ at panicle initiation, and 40 kg ha⁻¹ at flowering in the DS; and as 30 kg ha⁻¹ as basal, 30 kg ha⁻¹ at mid-tillering, and 30 kg ha⁻¹ at panicle initiation in the WS. Twelve hills plot⁻¹ of these genotypes were artificially lodged using a Prostrate Tester (DIK 7400, Japan) at 10, 20, and 30 DAF of each genotype. Another set of 12 hills was kept erect using artificial support with bamboo sticks and ropes. The support was placed at 30 cm below the tip of the panicle to prevent natural lodging. As an embedded micro-plot experiment, all treated hills received the same crop establishment, fertilizer management, and cultural practices. Insects, diseases, and weeds were intensively controlled to avoid any yield loss. Data on yield and yield components were taken at maturity for each genotype.

Yield and yield components did not vary significantly due to artificial lodging compared with supported plants in the 2005 DS (Table 1). But, in general, higher grain yield was observed in unlodged plants compared with artificially lodged plants. The highest yield was mainly attributed to a higher number of spikelets panicle⁻¹. The harvest index of the supported plants was also higher than that of artificially lodged plants. More severity of yield reduction was observed in plants lodged at 20 DAF than in those lodged at 10 DAF, with reduced spikelet filling percentage as well as harvest index, though the effects were not statistically significant. The reasons for the lack of significant lodging effects are probably that, when plants were lodged artificially, the favorable environmental conditions, especially higher solar radiation and lower precipitation prevailing during the DS in the Philippines, might have helped the lodged plants to straighten up again and re-establish growth to some extent. Roy and Jha (1987) also observed minimum yield loss in rice variety Sujata that was lodged at 10 DAF.

Significant genotypic variations in yield and yield components were observed in the 2005 DS (Table 1). Hybrid IR79172H produced the highest grain yield, whereas the inbred genotype PSBRc 28 produced the lowest. The high grain yield of IR79172H was attributed to its high number of spikelets panicle⁻¹, greater spikelet filling percentage, and larger grain size, despite it having the lowest number of panicles m⁻². The harvest index of this genotype was also high. Ponnuthurai et al (1984) reported that the higher yield of hybrids was attributed to their increased plant dry weight and harvest index.

Table 1. Effects of time of artificial lodging and genotype on yield and yield components of hybrid and inbred rice genotypes, IRRI, 2005 dry season.

Treatment	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Spikelets Panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet filling (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Harvest index
Artificial lodging						
Supported	7.53	444	100	76	22.6	0.48
L 10 DAF	7.09	449	93	76	22.7	0.47
L 20 DAF	6.56	439	93	73	22.6	0.45
L 30 DAF	7.20	444	98	74	22.7	0.44
Genotype						
PSBRc 28	5.97	483	88	66	21.5	0.43
IR75217H	7.21	451	94	75	23.1	0.48
IR79172H	8.10	397	106	83	23.3	0.47
LSD0.05	0.79	36	10	4	0.4	0.03
CV (%)	16	11	15	7	3	9
Artificial lodging	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Genotype	**	**	**	**	**	**

** Significant at P<0.01, ns: not significant, L 10 DAF = lodged at 10 d after flowering.

Significant variations in yield and yield components were observed between unlodged (supported) and artificially lodged plants during the 2005 WS (Table 2). The unlodged plants had 26% higher grain yield than early lodged (at 10 DAF) plants. The severity of yield loss increased from plants lodged at late flowering stage (at 30 DAF) to those lodged at early flowering stage (at 10 DAF). Unlike the experiment in the DS, reduced grain yield was observed in early lodged plants. This is probably due to the unfavorable environments, especially lower solar radiation and higher rainfall, accompanied by high wind velocity commonly occurring in the WS in the Philippines. The higher grain yield in supported plants was due to the significantly higher spikelet filling rate rather than more panicles m⁻² or more spikelets panicle⁻¹. The 1,000-grain weight and harvest index of early lodged (at 10 DAF) plants were lower than those of unlodged (supported) or late lodged (at 30 DAF) plants. These results suggest that yield losses from lodging are probably greater in the WS than in the DS, and that early lodging has greater detrimental effects on yield.

Distinct genotypic variation was observed in yield and yield-contributing characters of hybrid rice during the 2005 WS (Table 2). The highest grain yield was observed in IR75217H and the lowest grain yield was seen in SL-11H. Grain yields of IR75217H and IR79118H were identical. The high grain yield of IR75217H was due to its higher number of panicles m⁻² and higher spikelet filling rate rather than more spikelets panicle⁻¹ and higher 1,000-grain weight.

The harvest index of IR75217H was also highest. The high yield in IR79118H was mainly attributed to its high number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ and high 1,000-grain weight. The lowest yield of SL-11H was due to its lowest number of panicles m⁻².

Table 2. Effects of time of artificial lodging and genotype on yield and yield components of hybrid rice genotypes, IRRI, 2005 wet season.

Treatment	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Spikelets Panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet filling (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Harvest index
Artificial lodging						
Supported	6.35	347	110	69	24.7	0.45
L 10 DAF	5.02	328	107	60	24.3	0.40
L 20 DAF	5.37	333	109	62	24.7	0.43
L 30 DAF	5.96	333	109	68	24.7	0.45
LSD0.05	0.45	–	–	4	0.3	0.02
Genotype						
IR75217H	5.87	380	92	74	22.9	0.46
IR79118H	5.84	336	114	60	25.4	0.42
SL-11H	5.32	290	119	61	25.5	0.41
LSD0.05	0.39	15	5	3	0.3	0.02
CV (%)	10	6	7	7	2	5
Artificial lodging	**	ns	ns	**	*	**
Genotype	**	**	**	**	**	**

*: ** Significant at P < 0.05 and 0.01, respectively, ns: not significant, L 10 DAF = lodged at 10 d after flowering.

Yield and yield components did not vary significantly due to lodging compared with unlodged (supported) plants in the 2005 DS. But, in general, higher grain yield was observed in unlodged (supported) plants than in artificially lodged plants. Unlodged plants significantly produced higher grain yield than plants that were artificially lodged at 10 DAF in the 2005 WS. Higher grain yield in supported plants was due to higher spikelet filling rather than more panicles m⁻² or more spikelets panicle⁻¹. For hybrid rice, yield reduction could be anticipated if the plants lodged at the early grain-filling stage. Furthermore, the yield loss will be higher in the WS than in the DS due to the unfavorable weather conditions prevailing in the former, favoring greater yield reduction in lodged plants.

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